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Optimum Location Analysis for Ferry Terminals with Approach of Increasing the Functionality by Using S.W.O.T Technique and AHP Mathematical Analysis --Manuscript Draft--

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Question	Response

Conflict of Interest:

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Editorial Department of The Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics.

Dear Editor of the Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics; I am submitting a manuscript for consideration as publication in the Asian Journal of Shipping and Logistics. The manuscript entitled “Optimum Location Analysis for Ferry Terminals with Approach of Increasing the Functionality by Using S.W.O.T Technique and AHP Mathematical Analysis”. This research is self-funded and did not publish in any journal before, also this paper is considered as one of the fully accepted and presented papers at ICASL 2021.

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Optimum location, Ferry terminal functionality, Coastline management, AHP method, S.W.O.T analysis

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Title page:

Optimum Location Analysis for Ferry Terminals with Approach of Increasing the Functionality by Using S.W.O.T Technique and AHP Mathematical Analysis

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Abstract

The major goal of a ferry terminal is to serve transportation activities, besides many other important factors, it must be located in the right place. In this research the main purpose is finding optimum location for ferry terminals so: By field studies and published documents fifteen factors that may have the most effects extracted and then by using the S.W.O.T technique and related strategies also mathematical and psychological data and results based on the AHP method, rankings, weights, and results are calculated and sorted. As research, factors assigned to three locations at Persian Gulf coastal line with acceptable conditions and outputs presented as schedules and charts. Finally, the results are compared and the best output introduced as the most optimum location for regional ferry terminals.

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4 **1. Introduction:**
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6 The ferry operation is considered the most successful maritime operation in sense of its
7 transporting people, vehicle and goods. In many countries, a ferry is not just a transportation tool
8 but it is also used to maintain national integrity by providing access to remote islands that isolated
9 by water. A ferry operation needs terminals with specific properties to have optimum functionality
10 in its' operation and locating sites are very important and different from any other kind of structures
11 including urban and rural structures. Ferry terminals are one of the most important transportation
12 gates and their functionality can be affected by various factors and elements including their
13 location. So as an important infrastructure, selecting the right location during design studies would
14 be a vital factor. Even the best designs in the wrong places would be a huge failure and their miss-
15 operation roots in the studies and their location. In many cases during history, such malfunctioning
16 infrastructures had been abandoned after a very short period of utilization. So it is necessary to
17 consider the location of such expensive infrastructures in design studies very carefully, and such
18 studies can lead the project to efficient and effective results.
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24 In this research optimal locating solutions for ferry terminals compared and reviewed by using two
25 of the most well-known locating techniques including the "S.W.O.T technique" and mathematical
26 and psychological analytic hierarchy process know as the "AHP Method " also by using fifteen
27 most important factors that have the highest effects on ferry terminals functionality which
28 extracted from documents and studies, local field surveys and statistical data.
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32 **2. Research Method:**
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34 In order to evaluate proposed locations, fifteen influential factors including the required depth
35 of water, Possibility to penetrate in the waterfront, Access to coastal logistics facilities,
36 Maintenance and refueling conditions, Access to urban facilities and public transportations, Vision
37 and axis, Water and beach quality, Capability to expand the project, Distance from historical
38 context, Capability to build coastal backup installations and beach parks also temporary residential
39 camps, distance to the waterways with a minimum depth of 10 meters, were extracted by using
40 documents and field researches then by using S.W.O.T analysis and its' related strategies also
41 AHP method and weight of the factors in each proposed location analysis had been done and results
42 provided and sorted as tables, charts, and graphs. Finally, output results in both methods compared
43 and optimum strategies and the most desirable results are identified and presented as optimum
44 location and exponential fit for ferry terminals construction site.
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49 **3. proposed locations:**
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51 Considering the requirements and the information gathered base on the researcher's access to
52 the area, research method, and field surveys, three areas are presented for analyzing the influential
53 factors. After examining factors and their weights for all presented locations, optimal location will
54 be selected. to emphasis on accuracy of the answers and local access to field studies and details, it
55 was preferred to select proposed areas from the Persian Gulf and southern coastlines of Iran.
56 Therefore, three locations at Bushehr city Shoreline nominated by using aerial maps respectively
57 at North Shore Line, West Shore Line, and South Shore Line. The table for suggested locations
58 presented as below:
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Proposed locations	Attributes	Pictures
<p><u>Location No.1</u></p> <p>The area is located in the northern part of Bushehr city. Near to Bushehr customs administration and historical context.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Sandy beach and shallow waters, easy access to waterfront structures and capability to penetrate in sea 2- Access to the anchorage and dredged waterway canal 3- Proper security 4- Close to historical context and downtown 5- Ability to use maritime logistics installations 6- Easy access to municipal services 7- Appropriate vision and axis 	<p>Picture 1: Location of area No.1</p>
<p><u>Location No.2</u></p> <p>The area is located in the western part of Bushehr city on a coastal road, near to the airport and non-residential area.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Shallow waters and Sandy seabed 2- Capable for every kind of ships that needs minimum 5m waterline 3- Suitable depth and area of waters for anchorage 4- Appropriate distance to urban, also minimum environmental pollutions 5- Good quality of water, coastline, location access, and transportation 6- Capable to expand the project, installations & services like parks, camps, and labs 7- Capable for establish a dredged water canal for ships that require more than 5m waterline 	<p>Picture 2: Location of area No.2</p>
<p><u>Location No.3</u></p> <p>The area is located in southern part of Bushehr city and next to drink water desalt, and purifying installations.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Shallow waters and coral seabed 2- Short distance and direct path to appropriate depth of 5.5m 3- Appropriate access to public services and transportations 4- Good quality of water and coastline 5- Capability to locate anchorage at a short distance with required area 6- Possibility to expand installations, parks and camps 7- Capable to create the shortest dredged canal to waterways path with minimum depth of 10m 	<p>Picture 3: Location of area No.3</p>

Table No.1: Introduction of proposed locations (Author, 2020)

4. S.W.O.T technique and related strategies:

4-1. S.W.O.T analysis for location No.1:

Factors are analyzed base on the S.W.O.T technique and all four possible strategies for location No.1 are concluded:

	<p align="center"><u>Strength points “S”</u></p> <p>S1- Low depth and sandy seabed also easy access to marine and repair installations.</p> <p>S2- Short distance to anchorage via water canal.</p> <p>S3- Proper security and control.</p> <p>S4- Proximity to the Old Town and Downtown.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Weakness points “W”</u></p> <p>W1- Long-distances to suitable depths and waterways path.</p> <p>W2- Interference in path with cargo ships and oil tankers.</p> <p>W3- High cost of development based on limit area.</p> <p>W4- High cost to build coastal structures, parks, and camps due to urban density and poor water quality.</p>
<p align="center"><u>Opportunities “O”</u></p> <p>O1- Capability to use a dredged waterway canal with proper depth.</p> <p>O2- Capability to use maritime logistics installations.</p> <p>O3- Easy access to public and municipal services.</p> <p>O4- Capability to create a good vision and axis.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategy Based on S/O</u></p> <p>-Capable to use dredged canal and easy advance of waterfront installations in shallow waters.</p> <p>-Capable to use in common marine anchorage and logistics installations with shipping customs administration such as maintenance, refueling, marine protection and more.</p> <p>-Close to the urban texture and historical part of the city which helps to create acceptable view and axis.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategy Based on W/O</u></p> <p>-Use of dredged waterway Canal and long-distance to the appropriate depth of water for shipping.</p> <p>-Using maritime logistics installations besides interference with cargo ships and oil tankers.</p> <p>-Use of public facilities and good vision and axis by ignoring coastal structures, parks, and camps.</p>
<p align="center"><u>Threats “T”</u></p> <p>T1- Increase noise and environmental pollutions for the urban area.</p> <p>T2- interference with shipping customs office installations and passive defense issues.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategy Based on S/T</u></p> <p>-Easy advance in shallow waters and coral seabed for structures and access to dredged water canal without considering passive defense issues, environmental and noise pollutions also interfere with basic installations.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategy Based on W/T</u></p> <p>-Choosing location based on long-distance to appropriate depth of water for shipping and interfering with other vessels beside increase noise and environmental pollution also ignores future expansion due to urban density, poor quality of water and needed depth of water.</p>

Table No.2: S.W.O.T analysis for location No. 1 (Author, 2020)

4-2. S.W.O.T analysis for location No.2:

Factors are analyzed base on the S.W.O.T analysis and all four possible strategies for location No.2 are concluded:

	<p align="center"><u>Strength Points “S”</u></p> <p>S1- Cost-effective development of waterfront structures due to shallow water segments.</p> <p>S2- Direct access to appropriate water depths for ships with 50m length and 5m waterline.</p> <p>S3- Capable to create anchorage with sufficient area and proper depth of water.</p> <p>S4- Appropriate distance to urban and residential context</p> <p>S5- Good quality of water and coastline.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Weakness Points “W”</u></p> <p>W1- Requires a dredged canal for ships that have over 50m length and 5m waterline.</p> <p>W2- Require independent and appropriate logistics and maritime security at coastal installations.</p> <p>W3- Higher impact of regional floods, storms, waves and regional winds due to depth of water.</p>
<p align="center"><u>Opportunities “O”</u></p> <p>O1- Capability to minimize all kinds of environmental and noise pollutions.</p> <p>O2- Easy access to the public transportation system.</p> <p>O3- Capability to develop proper vision and axis.</p> <p>O4- Capable to expand basic structures, parks, and camps.</p> <p>O5- Capable to build a cost-effective water canal for all ships that require more than 5m of water depth.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategies Based on S/O</u></p> <p>-Easy advance in waterfront for ships with 5 meters water line.</p> <p>-Capability to expand basic structures, parks, beach camps and services due to vast lands around.</p> <p>-Suitable location to access urban texture besides minimizing pollutions.</p> <p>-Access to the appropriate depth of water for ships with 5 meters water line.</p> <p>-Capability to build landscapes using appropriate water quality and coastline.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategies Based on W/O</u></p> <p>-Establishment of all logistics, freight and overhaul installations independently based on the effects of tidal levels, storms, regional winds, and waves also depth of water.</p> <p>-Create acceptable access, vision and axis also proper transportation.</p> <p>-Capable to build cost-effective water canal with the shortest distance to the needed depth of water for ships that need 5 meters water line or more.</p>
<p align="center"><u>Threats “T”</u></p> <p>T1- Capable of increasing environmental pollutions.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategies Based on S/T</u></p> <p>-Access to the appropriate depth, quality of water and coastline also possibility of increased noise and environmental pollutions.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategies Based on W/T</u></p> <p>-Build all require installations for the project and dredged canal independently based on impacts of storms, waves and winds also environmental and noise pollutions.</p>

Table No.3: S.W.O.T analysis for location No. 2 (Author, 2020)

4-3. S.W.O.T analysis for location No.3:

Factors are analyzed base on the S.W.O.T analysis and all four possible strategies for location No.3 are concluded:

	<p align="center"><u>Strength Points “S”</u></p> <p>S1- Cost-effective advance in waterfront due to shallow waters and coral seabed.</p> <p>S2- Very short distance to an appropriate depth of 5 meters.</p> <p>S3- Appropriate access to public facilities and transportations.</p> <p>S4- Good quality of water and coastline.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Weakness Points “W”</u></p> <p>W1- Long-distance to exist coastal logistics and overhaul installations.</p> <p>W2- Lack of good vision and axis.</p> <p>W3- Long-distance to the north of the city and lack of easy access.</p>
<p align="center"><u>Opportunities “O”</u></p> <p>O1- Capable to create anchorage with short distance to the location.</p> <p>O2- Capable to establish coastal structures, parks, and camps.</p> <p>O3- Capable to build the shortest canal to waterways with a depth of more than 10m.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategy Based on S/O</u></p> <p>-Easy advance on the coral seabed to build waterfront structures at a suitable distance and area.</p> <p>-Very short distance to deep waters with a depth of more than 10 meters.</p> <p>-Capable to build basic structures based on the good quality of water and coastline also vast unused area.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategy Based on W/O</u></p> <p>-Require to build dedicated logistics and refueling installations at a short distance from the harbor and waterways.</p> <p>-Capable to build parks and camps without proper vision and axis also centrality.</p>
<p align="center"><u>Threats “T”</u></p> <p>T1- Proximity to water desalt treatment plants and the risk of increasing pollutions.</p> <p>T2- Disturb urban areas by adding noise and environmental pollutions.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategy Based on S/T</u></p> <p>-Easy advance on waterfront based on coral seabed and shallow waters without considering water treatment and desalt installations and risk of increase the pollutions.</p> <p>-Using good water quality and coastline also access to urban facilities without considering increasing noise and environmental pollution of urban areas.</p>	<p align="center"><u>Strategy Based on W/T</u></p> <p>-Long-distance to logistics, refueling, ship maintenance and overhaul installations and proximity to water treatment and desalt plants that increase the risk of pollutions.</p> <p>-Located in a short distance from the residential areas of the city and did not consider pollutions, easy access also vision and axis.</p>

Table No.4: S.W.O.T analysis for location No. 3 (Author, 2020)

5. Mathematical and Psychological Analysis using AHP Method:

5.1 Analysis and sorting the proposed locations using the Analytic Hierarchy Process:

Expert Choice is used as software for evaluation and giving weight to all analyzed factors, then results considered in the AHP method. In the results and outputs, the scoring is based on superiority. That means, the highest weight and score belongs to the most appropriate location, and the lowest weight and score belongs to the most inappropriate location. For the high accuracy in answers, the acceptable level of overall inconsistency is set to smaller than 0.2, the importance of the factors and conditions of each analyzed element also results for all three proposed locations are presented as graphs and tables:

Appropriate water depth:

Depth of Water	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0.230	3
Location 2	0.361	2
Location 3	0.409	1

Table No.5: Water depth (Author, 2020)

Graph No.1: Water depth (Author, 2020)

Capability to advance in the waterfront:

Possibility to penetrate in sea	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0.333	2
Location 2	0.301	3
Location 3	0.366	1

Table No.6: Advance in waterfront (Author, 2020)

Graph No.2: Advance in waterfront (Author, 2020)

Access to coastal and logistics installations:

Access to logistic installation	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0.459	1
Location 2	0.304	2
Location 3	0.237	3

Table No.7: Access to installations (Author, 2020)

Graph No.3: Access to installations (Author, 2020)

Access to the location of the site:

Site Access	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0.397	1
Location 2	0.352	2
Location 3	0.251	3

Table No.8: Location Access (Author, 2020)

Graph No.4: Location Access (Author, 2020)

Access to transportation facilities:

Transportations	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0.380	1
Location 2	0.355	2
Location 3	0.264	3

Table No.9: Access to transportation (Author, 2020)

Graph No.5: Access to transportation (Author, 2020)

Vision & Axis of the site:

Vision & Axis	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/388	1
Location 2	0/376	2
Location 3	0/236	3

Table No.10: Vision & Axis (Author, 2020)

Graph No.6: Vision & Axis (Author, 2020)

Water and coastline quality:

Water & Coastal edge quality	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/189	3
Location 2	0/461	1
Location 3	0/350	2

Table No.11: Water and coastline quality (Author, 2020)

Graph No.7: Water and coastline quality (Author, 2020)

Project expansion possibility:

Possibility to expand the project	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/250	3
Location 2	0/474	1
Location 3	0/276	2

Table No.12: Project Expansion (Author, 2020)

Graph No.8: Project Expansion (Author, 2020)

Distance to Historical Context:

Distance to Monuments	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/411	1
Location 2	0/377	2
Location 3	0/212	3

Table No.13: Distance to monuments (Author, 2020)

Graph No.9: Distance to monuments (Author, 2020)

Capability for establishing coastal installations:

Coastal Structures	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/260	3
Location 2	0/421	1
Location 3	0/319	2

Table No.14: Offshore installations (Author, 2020)

Graph No.10: Offshore installations (Author, 2020)

Distance to waters with a minimum depth of 10M:

Distance to Depth of over 10 meter	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/253	3
Location 2	0/335	2
Location 3	0/412	1

Table No.15: Distance to 10m Depth (Author, 2020)

Graph No.11: Distance to 10m Depth (Author, 2020)

The amount of noise pollution:

Sound Pollution	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/260	3
Location 2	0/421	1
Location 3	0/318	2

Table No.16: Sound Pollution (Author, 2020)

Graph No.12: Sound Pollution (Author, 2020)

The amount of environmental pollution:

Environmental Pollution	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/252	3
Location 2	0/397	1
Location 3	0/351	2

Table No.17: Environmental Pollution (Author, 2020)

Graph No.13: Environmental Pollution (Author, 2020)

Distance to Anchorage:

Distance to Anchorage	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/320	3
Location 2	0/330	2
Location 3	0/350	1

Table No.18: Distance to Anchorage (Author, 2020)

Graph No.14: Distance to Anchorage (Author,2020)

Distance to residential and urban context:

Distance to Residential Area	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/216	3
Location 2	0/473	1
Location 3	0/311	2

Table No.19: Distance to urban (Author, 2020)

Synthesis with respect to: Distance to Residential Area
(Goal: Choose Best Site fo > Distance to Residential A)
Overall Inconsistency = .02

Graph No.15: Distance to urban (Author, 2020)

Sorted ranking table for factors from the most important to the least important which used to select the optimum location presented below:

Analyzed Factors	Weight in Location 1	Weight in Location 2	Weight in Location 3
Appropriate depth of water	0/230	0/361	0/409
Capability to advance in the waterfront	0/333	0/301	0/366
Access to coastal logistics installations	0/459	0/304	0/237
Access to the location of the site	0/397	0/352	0/251
Access to transportation facilities	0/380	0/355	0/264
Vision and axis of the site	0/388	0/376	0/236
Water and coastline quality	0/189	0/461	0/350
Project expansion possibility	0/250	0/474	0/276
Distance to the historical context	0/411	0/377	0/212
Capability to establish coastal installations	0/260	0/421	0/319
Distance to waters with a minimum depth of 10m	0/253	0/335	0/412
The amount of noise pollution	0/260	0/421	0/318
The amount of environmental pollution	0/252	0/397	0/351
Distance to the anchorage	0/320	0/330	0/350
Distance to residential and urban context	0/216	0/473	0/311
Total	4/598	5/738	4/662

Table No.20: Weight of Indicators Considered in Proposed locations (Author, 2020)

Synthesis with respect to: Goal: Choose Best Site for Project

Overall Inconsistency = .02

Graph No.16: Sorted indicators from highest to lowest (Author,2020)

5.2 Overall Weight in locations:

The total weight of the factors for all proposed locations are calculated above. According to all 15 analyzed factors also standard deviation of 0.02 that calculated by the software, the overall table for proposed locations according to the AHP method presented below:

Optimal Location	Weight	Ranking
Location 1	0/298	3
Location 2	0/387	2
Location 3	0/315	1

Table No.21: Total Weight (Author, 2020)

Graph No.17: Total Weight (Author, 2020)

6. Analysis conclusions and results:

In this research, a comparative study for organizing and analyzing the location based on mathematical and psychological methods had been done to increase the functionality of ferry terminals as well as transportation & shipping management and coastal and environmental preserve. So after extraction and evaluation of all important factors, based on reviews and compares by two of the best organizing and analyzing complex decisions methods to identify the most optimum location: The S.W.O.T method results clearly shows that the S/O based strategy for location number 2 is the strongest strategy among all other proposed strategies. Also, by the results with the AHP method, after considering overall-inconsistency of 0.02, the most important factors determined and indices sorted respectively as the most important to the least important factors, and location number 2 again selected as the most optimum location and exponential fit for the ferry terminal design area. Besides, according to the same results for both methods, we can conclude that there is no difference between the accuracy of the methods and it depends on the research case and goals to select any of the mentioned mathematical and psychological methods. although it seems it is necessary to analyze both weights of the factors and optimum strategies to have the best results as the most optimum location in design studies.

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